

A STUDY ON JOB SATISFACTION OF VILLAGE HEALTH NURSE WORKING IN SELECTED PRIMARY HEALTH CENTRE OF COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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Abstract:

Privileged human beings are the most special and complicated of all the creations of the omnipotent. Man though small is a unique system has got a striking difference that is mind. Men at work are not workers alone, they are basically human beings with different whims and fancies, like and dislike choice, preferences, expectations etc. so every organization must be aware this common characteristics of the human ware to be happy. That is men need a sense of satisfaction at his work. The study is based on job satisfaction of village health nurse working in selected primary health centre of Coimbatore district. For the purpose of study 100 people have been selected. A questionnaire was designed and primary data was collected for the study. The researcher found that there is shortage of medicine supply and equipment facility. It is found that without the adequate stock level of medicines they cannot serve public in a satisfied manner. The Village Health Nurse's plays an important role in preventing diseases in villages through conducting special camps, field visit etc.

Key Words: Health Nurse, Satisfaction & Public

Introduction:

Human factor is the main important of all factors of production. This importance is due to the following characteristics. First this is the only resources, which is able to produce an output more than its inputs. Man alone can produce through motivated creativity an output greater than the sum of this input. Second this resource is animate, activate and living. It is man alone who with his ability to feel think, conceive and grow shows satisfaction or dissatisfaction, resentment or pleasure or acceptance for all types of managerial action. Third HR is the most complex and unpredictable in its behaviour. A manager can get his worker's time but he cannot force workers enthusiasm, initiative, loyalty and devotion. Fourth, each individual has his own distinct background. The performance of human being and their behaviour engaged on a particular job is influenced by intangible psychological and social factors, such as family breeding, education, personal likes and dislikes, emotions and job conditions, the welfare facilities and privileges available to them, while at work, recognition of their work the wage salary they receive and above all job satisfaction and the material rewards or punishment they receive.

Job Satisfaction:

Human Resource Management, in the sense of getting things done through people, is an essential part of every manager's responsibility. Many organizations find it useful to setup a specialist section to provide an expert service in the performance of human resource function. Today, no member in the organization would disagree that people are the most valuable asset of the organization. But in reality many organizations it is found that these most valuable resources remain under utilized, undervalued and under trained. Fast changes are taking place in the business environment. An organization must have the ability to absorb these changes at a fast rate than in the past, not simply to prove its competency alone but to justify its existence in the dynamic business world as well. All organizations, whether large or small must ensure themselves that they have the competent people capable of accepting this challenge. Not only have the monetary benefited which holds an employee in the organizations but also the job satisfaction provided by the organization to its employees. Job satisfaction comes from working conditions, job security, fair wages, good promotion policy, job enlargement, job enrichment, job rotation, grievance redressed machinery, suggestions scheme and employee counseling can be used to increase employee morale and job satisfaction.

Statement of the Problem:

A satisfied individual naturally becomes happy and healthy human being. The same state of mind of human being is sought after by everybody everywhere, in organization which ensures healthy organization climate must ensure the psychological health of its worker. An organization which does not understand the problem of dissatisfied workers has to face several problems which ultimately affect the health service to public.

Review of Literature:

Ambrose et al. (2005) conducted a qualitative study to investigate faculty satisfaction and retention. The study focused on the faculty of a private university over a period of 2 years. Findings suggested sources of satisfaction or dissatisfaction clustered into areas such as salaries, collegiality, mentoring, and the reappointment, promotion, and tenure process of departmental heads. Howre and wigder analyzed in (2004) the dual factor theory of job satisfaction on methodological factual grounds which is evaluated is a review of the

literature. Results are contrary to the proposition that satisfies and dissatisfies are one-dimensional and independent. It is considered that the two factor theory is an over signification of the relationship between motivation and satisfaction.

Objectives of the Study:

In studying the job satisfaction of Village Health Nurse working in Primary Health Centre the following objectives are framed.

- ✓ To assess the work load and responsibilities of Village Health Nurse.
- ✓ To evaluate the co-operation extended by the public with Village Health Nurse.
- ✓ To find out the problems faced by Village Health Nurse.

Methodology:

The study is conducted using questionnaire as a tool for know about the job satisfaction of Village Health Nurse. For the purpose of study 100 people have been selected. A questionnaire was designed and primary data was collected for the study. The collected data was subjected to analysis. The questionnaire was finalized with the help of proper guidance and the data collection was done. The collected data was transferred to master table, from the master table the sub tables were worked out and the analysis was done.

Population of the Study:

The population of the study is Village Health Nurses in selected main Primary Health Centre's in Coimbatore district are as follows

- ✓ Arisipalayam
- ✓ Pooluvampatti
- ✓ Nalletipalayam
- ✓ Vaalparai

Sampling:

Out of 48 total blocks in Coimbatore district, researcher has selected 4 blocks namely Arisipalayam, Pooluvampatti, Nalletipalayam and Vaalparai. All the Village Health Nurse's of these 4 blocks are the respondents of this study. Convenient sampling is employed to choose the blocks.

Data Collection:

Primary data was collected with the help of a structured questionnaire from the respondents. A total of 100 questionnaires have been designed and to collect the required primary data with respect to 34 questions were administered to the respondents. Secondary data was collected from Text books, booklets, magazines, research articles websites etc.

Tools Used For Analysis:

The statistical tool used to analyse the data is

- ✓ Simple percentage
- ✓ Chi-square.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ Time limit is the main hindrance for the study.
- ✓ The study is confined to students Primary Health Centre in Coimbatore district. So generalization of the conclusion may be wrong.
- ✓ The services provided by each Village Health Nurse may change from time to time therefore the findings may not hold good for all time.
- ✓ The limitation of statistical tools used is also a limitation of this study.
- ✓ Above all respondent's hesitancy in providing information also proved to be a limitation of this study.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Socio-Economic Profile of the Respondents

S.No	Variables	No. of Respondents	Percent	
1	Primary Health Centre	Arisipalayam	23	23
		Vaalparai	38	38
		Pooluvampatti	14	14
		Nalletipalayam	25	25
2	Age	Below 30 years	2	2
		30 – 40 years	20	20
		40 – 50 years	66	66
		Above 50 years	12	12
3	Marital Status	Married	100	100
		Unmarried	0	0
4	Type of Family	Nuclear Family	98	98
		Joint Family	2	2
5	Educational Status	School level	10	10

		Graduate	1	1
		Post Graduate	87	87
		Diploma holder	2	2
6	Income Level	Up to Rs 10000	0	0
		Rs10000 – Rs20000	13	13
		Rs20000-Rs30000	81	81
		7Rs30000 and above	6	6
7	Nature of Employment	Permanent	100	100
		Temporary	0	0
8	Work Experience	0-05 yrs	11	11
		06-10 yrs	8	8
		More than 10 yrs	81	81

Source: Primary Data

From the above table it is interpreted that Majority 38% of the respondents are from vaalparai main primary health centre. The majority (66%) of the respondents are belongs to 40-50 years. We can expect more vacancies for this job the next ten years. All the respondents are married. The most of the 98% of the respondents are belongs to nuclear family. It is found that most of them are nuclear family because of their job. The study reveals that most of the 87% of the respondents are Post Graduates. This reveals that most of the village health nurses are good scale because they have studied PG degree. Most of (81%) the respondents are belongs to the income level of Rs.20000 and Rs.30000. So it is clear that majority of the respondents are having good standard of living. All the respondents are permanent. The majority of 81% of the respondents are having the work experience of more than 10 years. So it is clear that majority of the respondents are well experienced in their job and also it shows the respondents are senior in their job.

Table 2: Chi-Square Analysis

S.No	Variable	D.F	Significance
1	Nature of Employment and Public Reponse for Getting Treatment with the Respondents	6	Not Significant ^{ns}
2	Year of Experience and Pension Scheme of the Respondents	1	Significant ^{**}
3	Year of Experience and Basis of Promotion	4	Significant [*]
4	Educational Level and Basis of Promotion	4	Not Significant ^{ns}

Source: Primary data * - 10% level of freedom ** - 5% level of freedom *** - 1 % level of freedom

The result of chi-square test reveals that there is no significant relationship nature of employment and public response for getting treatment with the respondents. There is a significant relationship between the year of experience and pension scheme of the respondents. There is a significant relationship between year of experience and pension scheme of the respondents. There is no significant relationship between the educational level and basis of promotion.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The equipment facility to Primary Health Centre and Health Sub Centre are suggested to provide sufficiently and in time.
- ✓ The vehicle availability can be increased so that the VHN's are work without any hesitancy.
- ✓ It is suggested to supply the drugs as per the requirement and usage to centers.
- ✓ It is suggested to fill the vacancies then and there to reduce the workload of existing VHN.
- ✓ The grievance redressed can be improved.
- ✓ It is suggested to appoint additional VHN for above population limit HSC
- ✓ It is suggested to granting the award for best performance of VHN's.

Conclusion:

In my informal interview with the Village Health Nurse's I came to know that no recruitment has been taking place in the past 10 years. No staff was recruited in the place of retired nurses. More over according to the population growth no further appointments also made. Hence the existing Village Health Nurse has more work load and responsibilities towards the public. The relationship between public and Village Health Nurse is found good. A central relationship is found in most of the places between both the parties So that Village Health Nurse feels free to serve public. The researcher found that there is shortage of medicine supply and equipment facility. It is found that without the adequate stock level of medicines they cannot serve public in a satisfied manner. The Village Health Nurse's plays an important role in preventing diseases in villages through conducting special camps, field visit etc. They have good scope for promotion.

References:

1. Fred Luthans, Organisational Behaviour, 6th edition.
2. The Hindu Survey of Indian Industry, Page number- 6.6 to 6.23
3. "Human Resource Management," — T.N. Gupta, page number 8.6 to 8.8

4. Job satisfaction scales for effective management (concept publishers, New Delhi)
5. Personal Psychology, 1952, volume — 22 Page number 171.
6. Journal of Applied Psychology, 1969 60(4)
7. Human Behaviour at work, 6th edition — Page number 521- 523
8. C. B. Mamoria, Personal Management — Himalaya Publishing House.
9. L. M. Prasad, Organisational Behaviour Sultan Chand and Sons, New Delhi.
10. Stephen. P. Robbins, Organisation Behaviour — 7th Edition.
11. Dynamic Personnel Administration, Rudra Basavaraj.
12. Organisation Behaviour and Human Performance Volume — 13 — Page Number 225-230
13. Thesis submitted by Rangaswamy and Markandeyan in 1998.
14. K. Veerakumar & Dr. S. Shanmugapriya, (2014) article titled “A Study on Work Life Balance among the Dual Working Couples” Intercontinental Journal of Human Resource Research Review, Vol-II, Issue-XI, Nov-2014, P.No14-21
15. Dr. S. Shanmugapriya & G. Gnanaselvi (2015) article titled “Happiness and Enjoyment at work Place” International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research, Vol-IV, Issue-3(3), March-2015.P.No.77-89.
16. Dr. S. Devaki, (2016) “Energy Conservation – The Indian Perspective”, International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 1, Issue 1, Page Number 171-178.
17. Jothy Balan & Dr. D. Ram Kumar, “Emotional Labour: The Invisible Unpaid Work of Nurses and How It Affects the Job Satisfaction”, International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 179-185, 2017.
18. Jothy Balan & Dr. D. Ram Kumar, “Stress in Nursing Profession and the Emotional Labour Strategies”, International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Volume 2, Issue 1, Page Number 108-114, 2017.
19. Dr. S. Shanthakumari, “A Study on Consumer Buying Behaviour on Fairness Cream with Special Reference to Udumalpet Town”, International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Volume 2, Issue 1, Page Number 115-118, 2017.